

Kashmir Journal of Legal Studies (KJLS)

PEER REVIEWED AND UGC CARE LISTED JOURNAL

Vol XI, No. 1, July, 2024

Statement of ownership and other particulars

Place of Publication : Srinagar
Publisher : Kashmir Law College
Address : Khawajapora, Nowshera
Srinagar – 190011, J&K India
Ownership : Kashmir Law College

Acknowledgement

The College acknowledges with great appreciation the financial support by ICSSR for the publication of the previous volumes of VIII & IX of Kashmir Journal of Legal Studies.

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Printed by

Valley Book House

Hazratbal, Srinagar-190006

Onbehalf of

Kashmir Law College

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Editorial

In this dynamic landscape of Jurisprudence, we embark on a journey to explore the evolving legal frontiers that shape our societies. The articles in this volume delve into a diverse range of legal topics, offering insights that challenge conventional wisdom and pave the way for progressive change.

As the legal realm grapples with technological advancements, examining the intersection of law and emerging technologies is much needed.

In this respect, Kashmir Journal of Legal Studies has been contributing substantially in the field of legal education and research and serves as a repository for intellectual exploration and critical analysis. The Journal is being indexed by Indian Citation Index (ICI) as a sequel to its quality of content. It gives us immense pleasure to note that the ICI has authorized the college to use their Logo in this Journal which is duly acknowledged.

In a time when legal principles are continuously tested, our journal seeks to provide a platform for thoughtful discourse. This journal is not merely a compilation of articles; it is a testament to the intellectual curiosity and dedication of legal scholars. We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors who have contributed their expertise, the reviewers who have diligently evaluated the submissions and our editorial team that has worked tirelessly to bring this volume to fruition.

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Emergence of Space Law as a New Frontier in Criminal Justice System: An Analysis

Dr Manjit Singh*
Sahibpreet Singh*

Abstract

This abstract takes a deep dive into the abyss of space law, its evolution, basic principles and various challenges that it poses to human beings who have moved beyond their home planet. The paper also involves an examination into complex jurisdictional issues, how space weapons are classified and regulated, ethical considerations as well as environmental concerns such as space debris. In addition, it reviews existing legal frameworks including treaties and agreements such as the Outer Space Treaty and the Moon Agreement. Furthermore, the abstract critically discusses issues on exploitation, exploration of space and fair distribution of resources hence necessitating international cooperation. It also looks at the intersection between competition and law in outer space markets using a fascinating case study involving Intelsat versus Alpha Lyracom which brings out how antitrust laws operate within celestial territories. In conclusion, it offers recommendations that call for developing a comprehensive legal structure, institutional mechanisms and educational programs that would help to wisely handle cases of space jurisprudence thus guaranteeing responsible and peaceful and equitable tapping into cosmic resources for the good of the current and future generations.

Keywords: Space Law, Jurisdiction, Space Weapons, Exploration, Environmental Protection, Ethics in Space

Introduction

Space law concerns itself with outer space activities; and these include, among other things, the exploration of space resources, conflict prevention as well as resolution, environmental protection and international cooperation that leads to peace. The sources from which space law is derived include treaties and agreements between nations, national laws enacted by States concerned with space exploration and settlement, customary international law governing

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outer space activities and judicial decisions in cases involving matters relating to outer space.¹ Furthermore, it borrows significantly from some other legal disciplines such as public international law, human rights law, transnational environmental law and penal jurisdiction of states. When the Soviet Union launched Sputnik 1 in 1957 its first artificial satellite², this marked the beginning of a race between US AND USSR towards conquering the Space.³ These legal challenges together with its advancements have forced an action on international community therefore establishing COPUOS in 1959.⁴ Here is where you will find major negotiation forums for adopting international space legislation instruments⁵ like the present day five core treaty based global aerospace regime:

- i. The 1967 Outer Space Treaty, also known as the Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, entered into force and has been ratified by a hundred and ten countries by 2021. Space law is basically derived from broad principles and standards enshrined in the Outer Space Treaty such as liberty of exploration and exploitation of space by all nations, no entitlement to seize celestial bodies, due to its being a peaceful nature must be employed for only peaceful purposes, responsibility and liability of states for their activities in outer space; further obligation to cooperate concerning exploration and use of outer space; however, jurisdiction or control over those involved with such acts.
- ii. The Rescue Agreement came into being in 1968. As at 2021, it has been ratified by 98 countries. Under this agreement, states must provide assistance in case their astronauts are at risk, share information on the discovery of space objects inside their territories or high seas with the country from which they were launched and return them to their launching state at the request of such a state.
- iii. The Liability Convention, which was adopted in 1972 and will be effective from 2021 when it reaches a number of 98 parties. The Liability Convention sets down procedures and norms for resolving claims relating to satellite, rocket and debris accidents on

¹ Frans von der Dunk (ed.), *Handbook of Space Law* (Edward Elgar Publishing Ltd, Cheltenham; Northampton, 2017).

² "Sputnik launched | October 4, 1957," *HISTORY* available at: <https://www.history.com/this-day-in-history/sputnik-launched> (last visited November 24, 2023).

³ "The Space Race: Timeline, Cold War & Facts," *HISTORY*, 2020 available at: <https://www.history.com/topics/cold-war/space-race> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁴ "COPUOS History," available at: <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/copuos/history.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁵ "COPUOS," available at: <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/copuos/index.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

earth's surface or its atmosphere or against another space object or its personnel while in outer space. It prescribes strict liability of launching state for damage caused by it within the Earth's boundaries or to an aircraft, as well as a fault-based one for any injury that may arise in outer space. In addition, the term 'launching state' according to this convention refers to a state that launches a space object either itself or through its territory.

- iv. The Registration Convention was enacted in 1976 and has been ratified by sixty-nine countries by 2021. According to the Registration Convention, a launching state is obliged to notify the United Nations about its space objects and provide details regarding their fundamental characteristics, orbital parameters, and functions. Additionally, it creates an international registry of all space objects called UN Register on Objects launched into Outer Space (UNROOS). Maintenance of the register is done by the same.
- v. The Moon Agreement, known as the Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, came into effect in 1984 and currently has 18 signatories. It is based on the provisions of international space law. This treaty asserts that resources located within or on a celestial body belong to all peoples of earth equally and hence an international regime should be developed once they become exploitable. Also in this context, military bases are not allowed to be installed nor weapons tested or radioactive materials disposed on earth's natural satellite or any other cosmic object.⁶

The aforementioned key agreements are supplemented by other global instruments that deal with separate facets of space law.⁷ Moreover, there are also regional and bilateral frameworks that support and supplement the international space law system.⁸ Generally speaking, national legislation is mainly about authorization, surveillance and licensing of space activities; establishment of national aerospace organizations; allocation and utilization of space resources; national security considerations including but not limited to public interests; and fulfillment of international obligations.

The evolution of outer space jurisprudence is a reflection of the transformation in character and scale of space activities which has seen them become more diverse, complex and commercialized over the years. In addition, new actors such as developing countries, non-governmental organizations

⁶ "Space Law Treaties and Principles," available at: <https://www.unoosa.org/unosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/treaties.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁷ MA Xinmin, "The Development of Space Law: Framework, Objectives and Orientations."

⁸ Michael G. Faure and Karine Fiore, "The civil liability of European nuclear operators: which coverage for the new 2004 Protocols? Evidence from France," 8 *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics* 227-48 (2008).

(NGOs), and private entities have augmented the difficulties and openings for space law development and application. Space law's evolution mirrors the broadening of scope and privatization of space activities, as well as appearance of new players. This includes issues like legal fallout from acts committed in outer space; jurisdiction problems; types or classes given to space weapons; principles governing use of these resources from space; definition for debris in relation to it being a hazard or not while others are concerned with ethical considerations all that require closer attention by legal authorities as regards their regulation. Respect for human dignity & interests & rights, social responsibility & improving public awareness & education on said matters emerge as key aspects capable of addressing these issues. Such recommendations would also include but not limited to state policy makers, international institutions, private organizations like companies or corporations other than governmental ones (also called NGOs), academics who teach subjects pertaining to this field such universities where it is taught at various levels depending upon country, civil society among others mentioned above. This article aims to comprehensively analyze these issues and provide a critical analysis of the same. It also seeks to outline some appropriate remedies that can be adopted as well as suggestions on how space laws for criminal justice can be improved and updated.

Space Crimes and Jurisdiction

State or entity jurisdiction refers to the legal power of a state or an entity to control, judge, and enforce law over a certain geographic location, person or object. Applied law is the collection of laws that governs any specific case or dispute, which can come from different origins like international agreements, internal statutes, customary practices or past rulings of courts. One of the aspects in relation to space law emerging issues includes determination of jurisdiction,⁹ and the regulation of personal criminal acts in outer space,¹⁰ which may cause the administration of justice to face significant challenges,¹¹ the safeguarding of human rights¹², and the upholding of peace and stability.¹³ Space crimes are acts or omissions in the nature of hacking, sabotage, espionage, theft, assault and murder that contravene the relevant law causing harm to persons or property in space. Alternatively stated; space crimes include any acts or omissions which infringe upon the proper law and result in

⁹ P. J. Blount, "Jurisdiction in Outer Space: Challenges of Private Individuals in Space" (Rochester, NY, 2007).

¹⁰ "Exploring the problems of criminal justice in space - Room: The Space Journal," *Room The Space Journal of Asgardia* available at: <https://room.eu.com/article/exploring-the-problems-of-criminal-justice-in-space> (last visited Nov. 24, 2023).

¹¹ Danielle Ireland-Piper and Steven Freeland, "Star Laws: Criminal Jurisdiction in Outer Space," 44 *Journal of Space Law* 44–75 (2020).

¹² Annette Froehlich and Claudiu Mihai Tăiatu, "Human Rights and Space Law," in A. Froehlich, C. M. Tăiatu (eds.), *Space in Support of Human Rights* 1–47 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2020).

¹³ Steven Freeland and Elise Gruttner, "Outer Space Security," in R. Geiß, N. Melzer (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of the International Law of Global Security* 0 (Oxford University Press, 2021).

injury to people's lives and/or property all over outer space. These may be committed by astronauts, cosmonauts, taikonauts space tourists, space miners, space pirates, or space terrorists. Space mining is a common occurrence where theft can occur thus this might be considered a crime. Moreover while cyber attack cases are not frequent within the world of space exploration one would rather stay safe than regret what happened. Space crime means any act or omission which violates applicable law and causes harm to persons or property in outer space. Motives behind such acts may vary such as personal reasons such as mental illness; political; economic motives like greed for example: resource exploitation; ideological reasons like terrorism where groups use force against those they perceive as enemies thereby causing death destruction due religious beliefs. In addition some each different actions have different effects on human life because it harms them through destroying their food resources and ecosystems that support it: examples endangering safety health staff on board spacecraft object disrupting work objects placing country under risk. These crimes can be classified depending on their impact like jeopardizing personnel safety within spaceships affecting operations functions of these components threatening security stability activities breaching rights interests nations others involved into this process.¹⁴

Many legal issues will determine the reception of space crimes. Different factors like the kind and seriousness of the offence, where and under whose control it occurred, identity of the offender and the offended ones and their citizenships, any role played by launching state as well as flag state, availability of witness or evidence; law enforcement and judiciary cooperation within countries involved; enforceable procedures and substantive norms. The contemporary outer space law system has laid down general principles that could be employed to deal with crimes committed in outer space, such as the following:

- a) The Outer Space Treaty of 1967¹⁵, which is the main source of the international space law, under which there are several provisions that prevent appropriation of outer space and celestial bodies, require the use of outer space for purposes other than war, within a state's national jurisdiction it provides responsibility and liability of states over their national space activities, territoriality rights of states on their spacecrafts with the crewmembers as well as satellite disease on foreign objects and the cooperation in exchange to further explore more about outer space.¹⁶

¹⁴ Jonathan Lim, "The Future Of The Outer Space Treaty – Peace And Security In The 21St Century" (2018).

¹⁵ Jill Stuart, "The Outer Space Treaty has been remarkably successful – but is it fit for the modern age?" *The Conversation*, 2017 available at: <http://theconversation.com/the-outer-space-treaty-has-been-remarkably-successful-but-is-it-fit-for-the-modern-age-71381> (last visited November 24, 2023).

¹⁶ *United Nations Treaties and Principles on Outer Space*, (United Nations, New York, 2002).

- b) The Rescue Agreement of 1968¹⁷, which complements the Outer Space Treaty, obligates the countries to help astronauts in trouble; to notify and converge with launch site country on any space objects found within their territories or on international waters; and upon request, sending them back.¹⁸
- c) The Liability Convention of 1972 serves as a supplementary agreement to the Outer Space Treaty that outlines the mechanisms and protocols for resolving claims arising from damage caused by space vehicles such as satellites, rockets and scrap debris on Earth's surface; or to aircraft in motion, or out of persistence in outer space with another spacecraft or its crew.¹⁹ The Liability Convention imposes on the launching state an absolute liability in case of damage caused to aircraft or to the earth and liability of the launching state based on fault for damage caused in outer space.²⁰
- d) The Registration Convention of 1976, to supplement the Outer Space Treaty stipulates that any nation launching a satellite is obliged to register it with the UN and give details about its basic features, orbital elements and purpose.²¹ The Registration Agreement also creates the United Nations Register of Space Objects managed by the UN Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA).²²
- e) The Moon Agreement of 1984, uses the principles and rules of the Outer Space Treaty for celestial bodies including the moon. The agreement also provides more details on how to go about exploring, investigating and using other planets within this galaxy. According to the Moon Agreement, moon resources along with the moon itself are a common heritage of mankind. Further, it proposes that an international arrangement be set up to govern when such resources can be exploited on lunar surface (if possible

¹⁷ "RES 2345 (XXII)."

¹⁸ "Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched Into Outer Space," *Institute of Air & Space Law* available at: <https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/research/space-law/rescue-agreement> (last visited November 24, 2023).

¹⁹ Prasadha Marakani, "An Analysis to Determine Fault under the Liability Convention 1972," 9 *International Journal Of Legal Developments And Allied Issues* 82–9 (2023).

²⁰ Agnessa O. Inshakova, Ruslan A. Konygin and Alexandr I. Travnikov, "Reshaping the Institution of Liability in International Space Law," in E. G. Popkova (ed.), *Sustainable Development Risks and Risk Management: A Systemic View from the Positions of Economics and Law* 141–4 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2023).

²¹ Frans von der Dunk, "The Registration Convention: Background and Historical Context" *Space, Cyber, and Telecommunications Law Program Faculty Publications* (2003).

²² "RES 3235 (XXIX)."

in future).²³ The Agreement also prohibits creating military bases, testing weapons and dumping radioactive waste on lunar surface. It also extends to other celestial bodies.²⁴

- f) The International Space Station (ISS) Intergovernmental Agreement of 1998, which is a multilateral pact that governs the operation and utilization of the ISS by the participating countries, which is an intricate as well as unique space entity made up of numerous modules as well as elements provided by multiple states.²⁵ The The ISS Intergovernmental Agreement covers ownership, registration, jurisdiction and control of ISS, its elements; rights and obligations of crew members and users; compensation for damage caused to third parties, intellectual property protection, dispute resolution mechanisms.²⁶

However, space law cannot ignore various problems related to crime committed in outer space which include issues like defining such crimes and putting them into categories, dealing with jurisdiction as well as applicable law regarding them investigation procedures followed while prosecuting the offenders. These principles ought to be within a framework that includes punishment measures for rehabilitation after punishment has been meted out. The above issues must be reconciled in respect to equity, defense, assistance of humans as worthy beings and ability to reintegrate one into a wider society on space which has special peculiarities.

Warfare in Space And Weaponry

One of the most complicated issues in space law is the control of space weapons. This could potentially endanger world peace and security.²⁷ Any devices or systems, which can cause any harm to space objects or their signals, are considered as space weapons. These include any in-service or under development technologies that may be used for purposes of damaging, destroying, interfering with the functioning of these objects or otherwise affecting them. Any hostile or aggressive action involving the use or threat of use of space arms from outer space to space objects is called space warfare.²⁸ As a result, some general principles and rules can be found in the existing legal

²³ Ram S. Jakhu, "Twenty Years of the Moon Agreement: Space Law Challenges for Returning to the Moon" (Rochester, NY, 2005).

²⁴ Eleni-Anna Mavroei, "The Effectiveness and Applicability of the Moon Agreement in the Twenty-First Century: Will There Be a Future?," in G. D. Kyriakopoulos, M. Manoli (eds.), *The Space Treaties at Crossroads* 35–48 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019).

²⁵ Alexandros Eleftherios Farsaris, "The International Space Station (ISS) Intergovernmental Agreement as a Precedent for Regulating the First Human Settlements on Mars," in A. Froehlich (ed.), *Assessing a Mars Agreement Including Human Settlements* 63–74 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2021).

²⁶ "Peaceful Purposes in International Space Law,."

²⁷ Sa'id Mosteshar, "Space Law and Weapons in Space" *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Planetary Science*, 2019.

²⁸ Bill Boothby, "Space Weapons and the Law," 93 (2017).

order surrounding space that might also apply to these weapons. These include:

- i. The 1967 Outer Space Treaty forbids placing nukes or other means of mass destruction into orbit. It prohibits the same around earth or any other celestial body, on the moon, or in outer space. It only promotes peace. It bars setting up military bases, installations or fortifications. It also prohibits testing of weapons and carrying out of military exercises on such bodies.²⁹
- ii. The Multi-lateral Partial Test Ban Treaty of 1963 restricts nuclear explosions above ground, under water or in outer space. The only exception is the underground ones. It was enacted to avoid the radioactive fallout. It further strives towards nuclear disarmament.³⁰
- iii. The ABM Treaty is a 1972 bilateral agreement between the USA and USSR which greatly put limits on the development and deployment of anti-ballistic missile (ABM) systems aimed at shooting down or exploding ballistic missiles/their warheads while in flight.³¹ Based on a principle of mutual deterrence and strategic stability, the ABM Treaty was designed to avoid a race in nuclear arms and potential nuclear war. In 2002, US terminated the ABM Treaty to create room for missile defense against rogue states.³²
- iv. Environmental Modification Convention is yet another multilateral treaty formulated in 1977 to outlaw military uses of environmental modification techniques having widespread, long-lasting or severe effects such as weather modification, climate manipulation, ocean current changes, and seismic activity inducement.³³ It also provides for consultation among its parties on peaceful use of such technologies; sharing data and information on their research and development activities.³⁴
- v. The Moon Agreement of 1984 also forbids setting up bases, carrying out weapon tests, and dumping radioactive materials on

²⁹ "Outer Space Treaty of 1967," *available at*: <https://history.nasa.gov/1967treaty.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

³⁰ "Test Ban Treaty (1963)," *National Archives*, 2021, *available at*: <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/test-ban-treaty> (last visited November 24, 2023).

³¹ "Antiballistic missile (ABM) | Missile Defense, Nuclear Deterrence & Arms Control | Britannica," *available at*: <https://www.britannica.com/event/Anti-Ballistic-Missile-Treaty> (last visited November 24, 2023).

³² "Anti-Ballistic Missile Treaty," *Wikipedia*, 2023.

³³ "Environmental Modification Convention," *Wikipedia*, 2023.

³⁴ "Convention on the Prohibition of Military or Any Other Hostile Use of Environmental Modification Techniques (ENMOD) – UNODA," *available at*: <https://disarmament.unoda.org/enmod/> (last visited November 24, 2023).

the moon and other celestial bodies³⁵ as discussed in the previous section.

So, the existing space law may be insufficient to solve problems related to space weapons and warfare like classification of space-based weapons, prevention of military activities in outerspace and enforcement of international humanitarian and security law in outer space. Furthermore, there is a possibility that it will not guarantee accountability in respect to any acts committed during such kind of wars or the liability for damage arising from them.

Exploitation of Space

Space exploration is the study of celestial bodies and outer space. It involves the use different techniques that include satellites, probes, rovers, landers, orbiters or manned missions.³⁶ Space exploitation refers to employing space resources like minerals, water energy or data for various objectives such scientific, commercial³⁷, industrial or social³⁸. This present space law regime has certain general principles and regulations that may apply regarding the exploration and exploitation of outer space as outlined below:

- i. The Outer Space Treaty of 1967 in section 1 states that all countries no matter what their level of economic or scientific development is shall follow a policy of exploration and use of outer space for the benefit and in the interest of all mankind.³⁹ This treaty is also encouraging international cooperation and consultation in the conduct of states' space activities, and requires publicizing information on it to members of the scientific community across the globe.⁴⁰
- ii. The Moon Agreement of 1984 obligated states to take steps to ensure that no interference occurs with the equilibrium of the environment of celestial bodies such as the moon and also safeguard their scientific and cultural worth.⁴¹

³⁵ "Moon Treaty," *Wikipedia*, 2023.

³⁶ "Space exploration | History, Definition, & Facts | Britannica," 2023 available at: <https://www.britannica.com/science/space-exploration> (last visited November 24, 2023).

³⁷ "As private satellites increase in number, what are the risks of the commercialization of space?," *World Economic Forum*, 2022 available at: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/01/what-are-risks-commercial-exploitation-space/> (last visited November 24, 2023).

³⁸ Mahulena Hofmann and Federico Bergamasco, "Space resources activities from the perspective of sustainability: legal aspects," 3 *Global Sustainability* e4 (2020).

³⁹ *United Nations Treaties and Principles on Outer Space*, (United Nations, New York, 2002).

⁴⁰ Tanjirul Islam, "Outer space treaty of 1967: Having loopholes?"

⁴¹ Eleni-Anna Mavroeidi, "The Effectiveness and Applicability of the Moon Agreement in the Twenty-First Century: Will There Be a Future?," in G. D. Kyriakopoulos, M. Manoli (eds.), *The Space Treaties at Crossroads* 35–48 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019).

- iii. The 1986 Principles on Remote Sensing of the Earth from Outer Space, which is a non-binding framework for regulating remote sensing operations as well as their application, refers to sensing of earth's surface and atmosphere from space for any purpose,⁴² which includes enhancing environmental protection, improving land use and management of natural resources.⁴³ The Principles uphold all states' entitlement to remote sensing data and, those which carry out the sensor's activities must respect other states sovereignty and interest, particularly the state sensed. The Principles also foster internationalism in such studying processes and encourage exchange of information between countries or scientists.⁴⁴
- iv. In 1992, the UN General Assembly adopted additional regulations named The Principles Relevant to the Use of Nuclear Power Sources in Outer Space, which are some other guidelines not legally binding that are meant to govern the safety and environmental aspects relating to the use of nuclear power sources, for example reactors or radioisotope generators during outer space activity whenever accidents occur or there is a breakdown.⁴⁵ States using nuclear power sources in outer space must carry out a comprehensive safety assessment and do everything possible to avoid or reduce the chances of causing any harm to the earth, its surroundings or its people.⁴⁶ For the purpose of a given document, states must also notify other states and the United Nations Secretary General about their intentions and outcomes with regard to employing atomic energy in space so that they can team up or give emergency aid in situations of imminent calamity.⁴⁷
- v. The Declaration on International Cooperation in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space for the Benefit and in the Interest of All States, Taking into Particular Account the Needs of Developing Countries of 1996, is a non-binding resolution adopted by the UN General Assembly which is intended to confirm and advance international cooperation as well as solidarity principles and objectives when it concerns outer space activities especially for the

⁴² "Remote Sensing," available at: <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/topics/remote-sensing.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁴³ "Remote Sensing Principles," available at: <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/principles/remote-sensing-principles.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁴⁴ Joanne Irene Gabrynowicz, "Law of Remote Sensing," in E. G. Njoku (ed.), *Encyclopedia of Remote Sensing* 332–4 (Springer, New York, NY, 2014).

⁴⁵ "NPS Principles," available at: <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/principles/nps-principles.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁴⁶ "Principles on Nuclear Power Sources in Space,."

⁴⁷ UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space Legal Subcommittee (31st sess.: 1992: Geneva) Chair, "Principles relevant to the use of nuclear power sources in outer space:: Chairman's text." (1992).

interest and advantage of those countries which are still developing.⁴⁸ The Declaration acknowledges the growing importance of space science and technology to the economic, social and cultural development of all nations, as well as the need to increase developing countries' access and involvement in these activities. The Declaration also urges states and international organizations to broaden their cooperation and support in education, training, research, development and application of space science and technology; as well as assisting in information and data sharing between all states and scientists.⁴⁹

Therefore, the classification of space resources, their fair allocation and the conservation of cultural and scientific values associated with heavenly bodies are important. It is also important to ensure that all countries including underdeveloped ones participate in space study. These aspects must be given attention to avoid conflicts, protect interests and encourage cooperation.

Space Debris and Crime against Environment

Space law is highly concerned with issues concerning space debris and environment, which are among the most crucial that may pose immense risks to outer space or earth security as well as sustainability. This term 'space debris' means all human-made non-functional objects. It includes their fragments in Earth's orbit or reentering the atmosphere.⁵⁰ Environmental crime encompasses activities that are against regulations and laws that damage or pose risks to the environment such as pollution, waste disposal, smuggling of wildlife and logging.⁵¹ Space debris and environmental crime may be governed by the general principles and rules in the extant space law regime, such as the following:

- a) Concerning the space activities of one state, other states are to be taken into account in terms of the treaty on outer space of 1967, and they should prevent pollution of outer space or celestial bodies and any alteration that impacts adversely on the earth's environment due to foreign materials from other planets.⁵²
- b) The 1972 Liability Convention extends the possibility of joint and several liability between two or more launching states as well as recourse claims among them and advises discussions or

⁴⁸ "Space Benefits Declaration," available at: <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/principles/space-benefits-declaration.html> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁴⁹ "A/RES 51/122,."

⁵⁰ Rada Popova and Volker Schaus, "The Legal Framework for Space Debris Remediation as a Tool for Sustainability in Outer Space," 5 *Aerospace* 55 (2018).

⁵¹ Matt R. Nobles, "Environmental Crime and Contemporary Criminology: Making a Difference," 44 *American Journal of Criminal Justice* 656–69 (2019).

⁵² *United Nations Treaties and Principles on Outer Space*, (United Nations, New York, 2002).

negotiations for a quick and fair settlement of compensation claims.⁵³

- c) The Registration Convention of 1976 mandates the launching authority to notify the UN Secretary General about any adjustments in position or purpose of their space objects, for example when they are non-operational, de-orbited or re-entered into the atmosphere.⁵⁴
- d) The Environmental Modification Convention of 1977⁵⁵ stipulated that States Parties must take measures to prohibit the interference in natural balance of earth's environment and secure the scientific and cultural worth of the earth's environment.⁵⁶
- e) The Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines of 2007, were endorsed by the United States Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS)⁵⁷ which are not compulsory and give direction on how to develop, plan, put into practice or decommission space objects aimed at minimizing the production and accumulation of debris in space thus ensuring that this environment remains intact for future generations to come.⁵⁸ It further advises states and international organizations to examine, adopt and assess their national or regional policies and regulation on mitigation of space debris while cooperating with one another to share information about their activities in mitigating it.⁵⁹

Nonetheless, complete legal definitions, proactive preventive measures, robust detection systems and effective reparation strategies should be employed to address space debris and environmental crime. These challenges are compounded by the intricacies of international law, technological constraints, as well as varied global actors interests. It is therefore critical that these issues have to undergo rigorous academic scrutiny that is legally and practically grounded.

Ethics in Space

Ethics in space is a field of applied ethics that includes the moral and social questions related to human activities in external space as exploration, exploitation, colonization, militarization, and preservation. Ethics in space focuses on the values, beliefs, and standards that should determine how individual states or organizations or people should behave toward outer space

⁵³ "RES 2777 (XXVI),."

⁵⁴ "RES 3235 (XXIX),."

⁵⁵ "Environmental Modification Convention," *Wikipedia*, 2023.

⁵⁶ Pekka Haavisto, "Environmental Post-Conflict Assessments: A New UN Tool Developed by UNEP," in H. G. Brauch, P. H. Liotta, et al. (eds.), *Security and Environment in the Mediterranean: Conceptualising Security and Environmental Conflicts* 535–62 (Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2003).

⁵⁷ "A/AC.105/C.1/L.260,."

⁵⁸ Nicholas L Johnson, "Space Debris Mitigation Guidelines."

⁵⁹ Diego Zannoni, "Out of sight, out of mind? The proliferation of space debris and international law," *35 Leiden Journal of International Law* 295–314 (2022).

creatures as well as the implication of such behaviors for the Earth and its population.⁶⁰ Ethics in space is one of the emergent and relatively new branches of study, whose significance has been steadily increasing and gaining relevance with the growth and widening reach of space activities.⁶¹ Justification and motivation of space activities are important especially in respect to the common good, human dignity, rights and interests of all stakeholders. This includes present and potential life forms on other planets. Exploration and use of outer space should be driven by ethical reasons and goals with a delicate balance between the benefits and risks for the humankind as well as the earth. The intrinsic value is respected while taking into account that life can manifest itself in different ways in outer space.⁶²

Space actors have very big duties and responsibilities, especially in relation to the legal system, international relations, and public and transparent space events. It is important that countries, organizations and individuals be able to conduct business in space ethically with no ambiguity regarding what should or must be done. There should be a commitment to established and new rules of space law as well as dialogue between all actors involved in the sector. The participation of the public as well as civil society in space activities should also be promoted.⁶³

The importance of sustaining and taking care of outer space cannot be overemphasized, particularly in terms of the environmental conservation, resource control, and cultural upkeep about outer space and celestial bodies. Standards that offer a moral basis for avoidance or reduction of harmful consequences resulting from space operations on the external space environment should be established. It is important to look into equal sharing and usefully managing resources from outer universe besides protecting its scientific and traditional property.⁶⁴ It's prudent that the innovation and advancement of space technologies, concerning safety and security, social and economic impact, as well as ethical and legal implications of new and emerging space technologies be guided by ethical standards and criteria. This calls for anticipation and addressing of the social-economic impact from space technologies on vulnerable or marginalized groups.⁶⁵ We must identify and

⁶⁰ James S.J. Schwartz and Tony Milligan (eds.), *The Ethics of Space Exploration* (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2016).

⁶¹ Daniel Munro, "If Humanity Is to Succeed in Space, Our Ethics Must Evolve" *Centre for International Governance Innovation* available at: <https://www.cigionline.org/articles/if-humanity-is-to-succeed-in-space-our-ethics-must-evolve/> (last visited November 24, 2023).

⁶² Adam Greenstone, "Government Ethics and Sustainable Space Exploration," 42 *Northern Illinois University Law Review* 313–29 (2022).

⁶³ Larry F. Martinez, "Legal regime sustainability in outer space: theory and practice," 2 *Global Sustainability* e26 (2019).

⁶⁴ Johannes Wallacher, Stefan Einsiedel and Andreas Gösele, "Sustainable development: in space as on Earth?," 2 *Global Sustainability* e15 (2019).

⁶⁵ "Technology Innovations for Space Exploration,."

solve ethical and legal dilemmas and conflicts that may occur as a result of applying using space technologies such as privacy, liability, or property.⁶⁶

Case Study: The Intelsat Antitrust Litigation

Alpha Lyracom Space Communications, a privately-owned satellite operator sued Intelsat in the United States courts. It was a series of antitrust lawsuits filed by Alpha Lyracom Space Communications, a private satellite operator, against Intelsat, an intergovernmental organization that provides satellite communication services, in the United States courts during the early 1990s. The main issue was whether Intelsat had abused its dominant position in the global satellite market by engaging in anti-competitive practices such as price discrimination, cross-subsidization and exclusionary contracts among others against Alpha Lyracom and other private competitors.⁶⁷ This case study shows how difficult it is to control market access and competition for space actors, particularly in cases of inequality, exclusion, or discrimination. It also indicates the challenges faced when attempting to apply and enforce antitrust norms and rules in outer space, especially those pertaining to ambiguity, uncertainty or dual-use. This case study is also an insight into why there should be international coordination and cooperation among countries; it will help promote dialogue and collaboration between different space stakeholders such as industry players and governments.⁶⁸

The case study can be summarized as follows:

- i. PanAmSat, a satellite system by the private firm Alpha Lyracom, offered transoceanic video and data transmission services to clients in North and South America, Europe and Asia. It insisted to be the only independent competitor of Intelsat, a global satellite system run by an intergovernmental organization for its members. The company asserted that Intelsat was monopolizing or occupying a dominant position in the world satellite market and had misused its monopoly power by engaging in various forms of anti-competitive practices that were detrimental to Alpha Lyracom including: varying charges between customers dependent on their geographical area or links with Intelsat; using government revenue to fund commercial operations; exclusive agreements with clients which prevented them from opting for other providers.
- ii. Alpha Lyracom sued Intelsat in US courts, several times, for violations of the Sherman Act, Clayton Act and Foreign Sovereign Immunities Act which are key federal laws on antitrust in the

⁶⁶ Kai-Leung Yung et al., "A Systematic Review of Product Design for Space Instrument Innovation, Reliability, and Manufacturing," 9 *Machines* 244 (2021).

⁶⁷ Alpha Lyracom Space Com. v. Comm. Satellite, 946 F.2d 168 | Casetext Search + Citor, "available at: <https://casetext.com/case/alpha-lyracom-space-com-v-comm-satellite> (last visited November 26, 2023).

⁶⁸ Alpha Lyracom Space Communications v. Comsat Corp., 968 F. Supp. 876 (S.D.N.Y. 1996), "JustiaLawavailable at: <https://law.justia.com/cases/federal/district-courts/FSupp/968/876/1947246/> (last visited November 26, 2023).

United States. Alpha Lyracom prayed for injunctive relief, declaratory relief, and damages against Intelsat. It also requested the court to enjoin Intelsat from its anti-competitive behaviour and open up its satellite system to private competitors.

- iii. Intelsat sought to defend itself by arguing that it was not under the jurisdiction of the United States court system, because it was an intergovernmental organization which had immunity against any state laws, unless it waived such immunity explicitly. Intelsat also argued that it could not be bound by antitrust laws in the United States since its activities were not commercial or trade-oriented within the country. Instead, they involved providing public utilities to member countries and other clients as dictated by its international obligations and commitments. Further, Intelsat argued out that all what is meant when accused of being anti competitive practices are just lawful and reasonable exercises of its rights and obligations as an intergovernmental organization stipulated under its founding treaty and regulations.
- iv. The case experienced a lot of inconsistency in rulings by American courts on different aspects such as jurisdiction, immunity, applicability of antitrust laws and the merits of charges. The case went through many levels of appeal and review before being settled out of court in 1993 after Intelsat agreed to pay Alpha Lyracom \$10 million and modify some procedures to enable other businesses to compete with it in satellite-related activities.⁶⁹

The case study presents several regulatory challenges in space activities:

- a) Defining and classifying the activities of space actors like Intelsat and Alpha Lyracom, particularly in ambiguous or dual-use scenarios.
- b) Ensuring fair market access for all space actors, including developing countries and private competitors, and protecting them from potential abuses by dominant providers like Intelsat.
- c) Applying and enforcing antitrust and competition laws in outer space, especially in complex or uncertain situations.
- d) Promoting dialogue among all space actors and stakeholders, enhancing public and civil society involvement in space activities governance, particularly concerning antitrust and competition issues. This includes encouraging international cooperation among states and intergovernmental organizations involved in space activities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

⁶⁹ United States Court of Appeals and Second Circuit, "113 F3d 372 Alpha Lyracom Space Communications IncLp v. Comsat Corporation," F3d 372 (1997).

This research paper examines space law as a new frontier in criminal justice system. It also highlights some challenges that emanate from increasing and diversifying human activities in outer space. Additionally, it has explored some existing as well as emerging legal frameworks and mechanisms for regulating and governing such activities, with proposals for how they could be improved. Some of the possible solutions towards enhancing space law as a new frontier in criminal justice include:

- i. To establish a legal framework that regulates market entry and competitiveness of space participants, in particular as regards antitrust matters. It could bring about new arrangements or norms that articulate what constitutes the field of space, guarantee equitable admission to all space actors, apply rules against monopolies and engender dialogue among interested parties.
- ii. Creating the policy framework for governing space activities, with a particular focus on antitrust matters. This could entail establishing new or leveraging existing institutions that can control and arbitrate anti-competitive practices in outer space like COPUOS, ITU, WTO, or ICJ.
- iii. A more stringent research and analysis of space activities, especially on matters related to antitrust. This can encompass research or reports that shed light on the character, governing mechanisms and effects of space activities.
- iv. Space activities can be made more understandable to the society and public generally through education so that they can comprehend the antitrust issues concerning them. This may involve holding meetings or running programs that enlighten people about how space activities are regulated.

In conclusion, this research's objective is to offer a glimpse of space law and criminal justice in relation to human activities in outer space. Additionally, it is expected that this article has ignited the reader's curiosity on this mind boggling topic and stimulated further inquiry and study. Criminal justice believes that there are great opportunities for improving and progressing the legal system and humanity as a whole in space law, which is seen as anew frontier. In addition to being a common heritage, space law is also considered a shared responsibility of all mankind, meaning that it requires cooperation from all states or other actors with public participation to ensure its peaceful use by future generations.